

International Journal of Agriculture Extension and Social Development

Volume 5; Issue 2; Jul-Dec 2022; Page No. 24-29

Received: 20-05-2022
Accepted: 27-06-2022

Indexed Journal
Peer Reviewed Journal

A study on awareness and attitude of students towards online shopping

Nasratullah Kakar¹, DK Singh², Mohammad Akbar Nadeerpoor³, Israrullah Yousafzai⁴ and Rafiullah Rahimzai⁵

¹Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Agricultural Extension Education, College of Agriculture, University of Agriculture Sciences, Dharwad, Karnataka, India

²Professor, Department of Agricultural Extension, College of Agriculture, Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel University of Agriculture & Technology, Modipuram, Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India

³Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, University of Agriculture Sciences, Dharwad, Karnataka, India.

⁴Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Agribusiness Management, College of Agriculture, University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwad, Karnataka, India

⁵Lecturer, Department of Economics and Extension, Faculty of Agriculture, Nanagarhar University, Afghanistan

Abstract

In recent years, online shopping as a new consumption method accepted by more and more people. University students are becoming the major group of online shopping. So we need have a better understanding of the university students' awareness and attitude towards online shopping, so that companies which are doing or want to do e-commerce can take advantages from it. With the rapid development of network technology, electronic commerce and electronic marketing had been formed and developed gradually, thereby forming new business model and business chance which exerted an important influence on the country's economic future competitiveness. On-line shopping is a recent phenomenon in the field of E-Business and is definitely going to be the future of shopping in the world. Most of the companies are running their on-line portals to sell their products/services on-line. The facility of online purchasing has allowed customers to identify the different types of products available in the global market, Due to rapid globalization; all types of products are available on the internet. Goods and services, consumer durables, books, audio and video cassettes and services like and air tickets can also be purchased online. The paper aims to study about the consumer awareness, attitude and factors affecting on online shopping. The present research study has used Qualitative and Quantitative research methods to study the impact factors of consumers on on-line shopping, respondents, awareness and attitudes about the rules and regulations of online shopping and benefits and services of online shopping. The data were collected through Questionnaires. Simple percentage analyses have been used in the analysis. Results of the study reveal that on-line shopping in India is significantly affected by various factors like awareness, knowledge, attitude, use of ICT tools and motivational factors.

Keywords: University students, online shopping, awareness, knowledge and attitude

1. Introduction

Online shopping is gaining popularity as a new type of consumption. It is a type of e-commerce that involves browsing and searching for product information in a virtual online environment in order to offer enough information for a buying decision and then carrying out the purchase activity. Indian e-commerce market has been witnessing high growth during the past few years, a trend that is expected to continue with the value of e-commerce sales expected to grow by 21.5% to reach the value of INR5.5 trillion (\$74.8bn) in 2022, according to Global Data, a leading data and analytics company. E-commerce has transformed the way consumers shop in India in the last few years, supported by increase in Internet and Smartphone penetration, rise in digital literacy among consumers and government's digital push. The COVID-19 pandemic has further accelerated the shift towards online shopping. The emergence of new variant will further push people to opt for online channel.

Through the development in several years, many websites for online shopping are outstanding, such as Amazon,

Flipkart, Myntra, Snapdeal and so on. They encouraged the development of e-commerce in India. University students have more opportunities to utilize the internet and are more comfortable with computers; this provides the technological framework for them to engage in online shopping. Furthermore, university students are more open to new experiences. As a result, university students have become a significant demographic of internet shoppers. The goal of this research is to investigate the elements that influence university students' awareness and attitudes towards online shopping in order to give some practical ideas for internet or e-commerce enterprises to assist them gain a competitive edge in market decisions.

2. Related Theories and Research Hypothesis

2.1 Related Theories

Attitude is a taught proclivity to behave consistently favorably or unfavorably in relation to a certain object. It is a person's appraisal and behavioral predisposition towards certain items that stems from their moral concept and worth. It is commonly used to describe the direction of individual

behavior and is a key predictor of individual behavior. Attitude is the internal cognitive, effective, and cognitive response to external stimuli. Based on past studies, researchers discovered that perceived safety, website structure, pricing, and product quality all have an impact on customers' attitudes regarding online buying. The term "security" refers to the protection of the hardware, software, and data in the internet system against accidental or malicious destruction, modification, and leakage. In other terms, internet security refers to the protection of information in an online context. On the other hand, many consumers believe that they can always acquire cheaper items at an online shop since firms that sell products online may save a lot of money compared to traditional sellers on things like store rent, agency fees, wages, and so on.

Thirdly, because online shopping is a virtual form of purchasing, it is impossible for consumers to touch the real things while making a buy choice, which causes some consumers to be suspicious of the product's quality, and this suspicion, reduces their purchase action. The last component is website structure; the style, kind, compositor, colors, and so on will directly affect consumers' perception and stay time on the website, influencing their buy intention and conclusion.

2.2 Conceptual Framework and Hypotheses

The conceptual framework was constructed by the researchers based on a survey of the literature and prior investigations, as shown below:

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework

3. Material and methods

3.1 Research Design

In the present investigation, *Ex-post facto* research design was used. This design was considered as appropriate because the phenomenon has already occurred. *Ex-post facto* research is the most systematic empirical enquiry in which the researcher does not have control over independent variables as their manifestation has already occurred as they are inherent and can't be manipulatable.

3.2 Sampling Technique

The study was conducted in Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel University of Agriculture and Technology, Meerut of Uttar Pradesh, India. Respondents were selected by the random sampling method of the sampling technique, from all registered students of the university 30 respondents from each degree programme (UG, PG and PhD) were selected to make the sample size of 90 for the study.

3.3 Data collection procedure and period enquiry

The study was based on primary as well as secondary data. The secondary data was collected from the concerning while the primary data was collected with help of pre-tested structural schedule by personal interview method. Taking into consideration the various existing factor e.g. time and extent of available amongst the respondents, it was decided to adopt personal interview method along with schedule for the purpose of collection of data. A detailed schedule was prepared for collection of needed information. The schedule was developed in the light of the objective of the present

study. The schedule was pre-tested in the sampling population to the extent of about 5 percent of the total respondents and modified according to the need of study. The purpose of study was clearly explained to the respondents at the time of data collection.

3.4 Analysis of data and statistical tools applied

Information was arranged in tabular forms and interpretation and analysis were done usually in terms of percentage, average and chi-square.

3.5 Percentage

Percentage was used for making the simple comparison. For calculating percentage, frequency of particular cell was multiplied by 100 and divided by total number of observation or respondents. For example out of 90 respondents, 50 respondents used internet as source of information, percentage will be-

$$\text{Percentage (\%)} = 50/90 \times 100 = 55.56\%$$

3.6 Rank

Rank refers to the positions and their occupants arranged in a hierarchy or inequality.

Ranking item question are given to record the preference of the respondents, like multi choice question, they also contain number of alternative. The difference between these two is that in multiple choice questions only one of the answers is to be selected, but in case of ranking item question order of preference is to be given for all.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1 Level of awareness of the respondents about online purchase

Awareness of the respondents regarding various online purchase i.e. information and communication technology (ICT), Internet, online shopping, social network, mobile. Four questions about (ICT), four social network sites, and six electronic systems were taken into account to know their knowledge level.

4.1.1 Knowledge level of electronic systems

Data in Table-1 depict that majority (74.44%) of respondents had knowledge of e-library followed by 50 per cent had knowledge of e-governance, 37.78 per cent had knowledge of e-business, 35.56 per cent had knowledge of e-extension, 20 per cent had knowledge of e-tender and 14.44 per cent respondents had knowledge of e-procurement respectively.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents according to their knowledge level of electronic systems n = 90

S. No.	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	e-governance	45	50.00
2	e-library	67	74.44
3	e-extension	32	35.56
4	e-business	34	37.78
5	e-tender	18	20.00
6	e-procurement	13	14.44

4.1.2 Mobile type

Result in Table-2 showed that more than half (66.67%) of respondents had android type of mobile, followed by 20 per cent simple type, 11.11 per cent Microsoft/windows and

only 2.22 per cent respondents had any other type of mobile. It is clear that majority of students adopt latest technology in the field of communication.

Table 2: Distributions of respondents according to their mobile type n=90

S. No.	Mobile type	Frequency	Percentage
1	Simple	18	20.00
2	Microsoft/windows	10	11.11
3	Android	62	68.89

4.1.3 Knowledge about Internet

Table-3 indicates that majority (54.44%) had medium knowledge about internet followed by 27.78 per cent respondents had advanced (latest) knowledge, while 17.78 per cent respondents had novice (new) knowledge regarding

internet. It is clear that up to the some extent people are not interested in online shopping because they lack knowledge of internet, computers and modern technologies. The findings of Budzikowska *et al.* (2001) also support of the present findings.

Table 3: Distribution of respondent according to their knowledge about internet. n=90

S. No.	Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
1	Novice (new knowledge)	16	17.78
2	Intermediate (medium knowledge)	49	54.44
3	Advanced (latest)	25	27.78

4.1.4 Place of internet use

From the Table-4 clear that majority (95.56%) respondents used internet in their hostel, followed by 24.44 per cent used outside university, 22.22 per cent used in computer section,

21.11 per cent used in library, while 18.89 percent respondents used internet in department. It can be concluded that Wi-Fi facility provides to hostel are promotion student accessibility more.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents according to their place of internet use n = 90

S. No.	Place	Frequency	Percentage
1	Library	19	21.11
2	Hostel	86	95.56
3	Department	17	18.89
4	Outside university	22	24.44
5	Computer section	20	22.22

4.1.5 Time spend for using internet

It is evident from Table-5 that majority (36.67%) of respondents using internet 1-2 hours every day followed by

23.33 per cent less than one hour, 21.11 per cent 2-3 hours, 10 per cent 3-4 hours and 08.89 per cent respondents using internet more than 4 hours.

Table 5: Distribution of time for using internet of respondents every day. n=90

S. No.	Time	Frequency	Percentage
1	Less than one hour	21	23.33
2	1-2 hour	33	36.67
3	2-3 hour	19	21.11
4	3-4 hour	9	10.00
5	More than 4 hour	8	08.89

4.1.6 Use of ICTs

The Table-6 indicates that using of social network, the respondent possessed higher using score WhatsApp (231) followed by Facebook (227), e-mails (222) and twitter (123)

respectively. Thus, it is clear that WhatsApp is most popular among students in comparison to Facebook, emails and twitter.

Table 6: Distribution of respondents according to the use of ICTs n = 90

S. No.	Website	Using			Total Score	Mean Score	Rank Order
		Often	Sometime	Never			
1	WhatsApp	53	35	2	231	2.56	I
2	e-mails	48	36	6	222	2.46	III
3	Facebook	49	39	2	227	2.52	II
4	Twitter	3	27	60	123	1.36	IV

4.1.7 Online shopping during last one year

The result in Table-7 revealed that more than half (53.33%) of respondents shop online ones in a three months during

last one year followed by 36.66 per cent ones in sixth months and 10.00 per cent ones in year during last one year.

Table 7: Distribution of respondents according to having online shopping during last one year n=90

S. No.	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Ones in A three months	48	53.33
2	Ones in a sixth month	33	36.66
3	Ones in a year	9	10.00

4.1.8 Online shopping Need

The purchase of respondents through online was calculated in table-8 The results revealed that in part of clothes in the table shirt score possessed higher score (178) followed by Jeans (153), Trousers (137), Jacket (134) and Sweaters possess (128) scores.

In part of electronic products in the table Mobile score possessed higher score (151) followed by pen drive (115), Laptop computer (112), Tablet (105), Printer (101), IPod (99) and Desktop computer possessed (97) scores.

In part of tickets in the table Railway ticket score possessed higher score (211) followed by Bus ticket (136), Hotel/ Guest house reservation (125) and Airplane ticket possessed (116) scores.

In part of others in the table Books score possessed higher score (191) ranked first followed by Electronic gadgets (135) with second ranked, Toys (110), Cosmetics (106) and Groceries possessed (101) scores. Jones (2003) study also supports present findings respectively.

Table 8: Distribution of respondents according to their online shopping need n = 90

S. No.	Products	Purchased online			Total Score	Mean Score	Rank Order
		Always	Sometime	Never			
A. Clothes							
1	Jeans	17	29	44	153	1.70	II
2	Shirt	29	30	31	178	1.97	I
3	Trousers	12	23	55	137	1.52	III
4	Jacket	12	20	58	134	1.48	IV
5	Sweaters	09	20	61	128	1.42	V
B. Electronic products							
1	Printer	01	09	80	101	1.12	V
2	Desktop computer	00	07	83	97	1.07	VII
3	Laptop computer	03	16	71	112	1.24	III
4	Pen drive	04	17	69	115	1.27	II
5	Mobile	10	31	59	151	1.67	I
6	Tablet	00	15	75	105	1.16	IV
7	IPod	00	9	81	99	1.1	VI
C. Tickets							
1	Airplane ticket	07	12	71	116	1.28	IV
2	Railway ticket	43	35	12	211	2.34	I

3	Bus ticket	12	22	56	136	1.51	II
4	Hotel/ Guest house reservation	09	17	64	125	1.38	III
D. Others							
1	Groceries	01	09	80	101	1.12	V
2	Cosmetics	01	14	75	106	1.17	IV
3	Books	32	37	21	191	2.12	I
4	Electronic gadgets	05	35	50	135	1.5	II
5	Toys	04	12	74	110	1.22	III

4.1.9 Amount spend on a single online purchase

Data in Table-9 depicted that majority of (54.44%) respondents were spend less than Rs.1000 on a single online purchase followed by 27.77 per cent 1000-3000, 14.44 per cent 3000-5000 and 03.33 per cent respondents spend more than Rs.5000 on a single online purchase.

Groceries possess (101) scores. Jones (2003) study also supports present findings.

Table 9: Distribution of Approximate maximum amount spend on a single online purchase n = 90

S. No.	Amount	Frequency	Percentage
1	Less than Rs 1000	49	54.44
2	1000-3000	25	27.77
3	3000-5000	13	14.44
4	More than 5000	03	03.33

4.1.10 Payment mode

The results in Table-10 clearly states that majority (82.22%)

respondents paid by cash on delivery followed by 35.55 per cent net banking, 31.11 per cent debit card and 15.55 per cent respondents paid by credit card.

Table 10: Payment mode normally adopted by respondents when shopping online n = 90

S. No.	Payment mode	Frequency	Percentage
1	Credit card	14	15.55
2	Debit card	28	31.11
3	Net banking	32	35.55
4	Cash on delivery	74	82.22

4.1.11 Favourite site for online shopping

The data in Table-11 indicates that ranking of online sites the Flip kart.com possessed higher score of (503) ranked first, followed by Amazon. In (472), Snapdeal.com (454), eBay. in (411), Homeshop 18.com (397) and Myntra.com possessed (301) scored second, third, fourth, fifth and sixth rank respectively.

Table 11: Ranking of favourite site for online shopping n = 90

S. No.	Online Site	Rank						Total Score	Mean Score	Rank Order
		1	2	3	4	5	6			
1	Flip kart.com	75	5	2	5	2	1	503	5.58	I
	Percentage	83.33	5.55	2.22	5.55	2.22	1.11			
2	eBay. in	38	18	9	13	6	6	411	4.56	IV
	Percentage	42.22	20	10	14.44	6.66	6.66			
3	Amazon. In	63	8	5	8	4	2	472	5.24	II
	Percentage	70	8.88	5.55	8.88	4.44	2.22			
4	Homeshop 18.com	24	21	28	6	7	4	397	4.41	V
	Percentage	26.66	23.33	31.11	6.66	7.77	4.44			
5	Snapdeal.com	55	12	6	9	5	3	454	5.04	III
	Percentage	61.11	13.33	6.66	10	5.55	3.33			
6	Myntra.com	16	6	27	9	4	28	301	3.34	VI
	Percentage	17.77	6.66	30	10	4.44	31.11			

4.1.12 Motivational factors towards online purchase

The Table-12 shows that more than half (58.89%) of respondents motivational factor toward online purchase was convenience and saves time followed by 46.67 per cent low

price, 24.44 per cent not available in local store, 14.44 per cent fast shipping of products, 13.33 per cent friend referral and only 6.67 per cent respondents motivational factor toward online purchase was trust with online store.

Table 12: Distribution of respondents according to their motivational factors towards online purchase n = 90

S. No.	Motivational factors	Frequency	Percentage
1	Low price	42	46.67
2	Convenience & saves time	53	58.89
3	Fast shipping of products	13	14.44
4	Trust with online store	06	06.67
5	Not available in local store	22	24.44
6	Friend referral	12	13.33

4.2 Attitude towards online purchase

Consumer attitudes are a composite of a consumer’s beliefs about, feelings about, and behavioural intentions toward some object-within the context of marketing, usually a brand or retail store. These components are viewed together since they are highly interdependent and together represent forces that influence how the consumer will react to the object.

4.2.1 Attitude and level of agreement regarding online purchase

The results in Table-13 indicates that level of agreement of respondent about questions, the respondents possessed higher agreement score Shopping on internet saves time (154) ranked first followed by It is great advanced to be able

to shop at any time of the day (152) ranked second, I prefer cash on delivery than payment via credit/debit card (138) ranked third, Selection of goods available on the online is very broad (119) ranked fourth, Internet reduces the monetary cost of traditional shopping (111) ranked fifth, Online purchase infrastructure in India is underdeveloped (108) ranked sixth, Online purchase is risky (104) ranked seventh, Necessity of having bank account or credit creates difficulty (103) ranked eighth, A long time is required for the delivery of products and services (98) ranked ninth, While shopping online I hesitate to give my credit card number (97) scores with tenth ranked respectively. Thus, it is clear from the table that online purchase is more convenient and save times. Heijden (2003), Horrigan (2008) rivalled the same findings.

Table 13: Distribution of respondent according to their attitude and level of agreement regarding online purchase n = 90

S. No.	Questions	Level of agreement			Total Score	Rank Order
		Agree	Un decided	Disagree		
1	Online purchase saves time.	75	4	11	154	I
2	Online purchase can be done at any time of the day.	72	8	10	152	II
3	Online purchase is risky	44	16	30	104	VII
4	A long time is required for the delivery of products and services.	39	20	31	98	IX
5	Selection of goods available on the online is very broad.	54	11	25	119	IV
6	While shopping online I hesitate to give my credit card no.	39	19	32	97	X
7	Internet reduces the monetary cost of traditional shopping.	47	17	26	111	V
8	Necessity of having bank account or credit creates difficulty.	41	21	28	103	VIII
9	I prefer cash on delivery than payment via credit/debit card.	66	6	18	138	III
10	Online purchase infrastructure in India is underdeveloped.	41	26	23	108	VI

5. Conclusion

On the basis of findings and observations made, it may be concluded that Majority of respondents had medium knowledge of internet, respondents use internet 1-2 hours daily at their respective hostels, maximum per cent of respondents were found to had Android type of mobile phones using WhatsApp as first choice followed by Facebook as secondary. Majority of respondents were found that they shop online once in three months for shirts, mobile, rail Tickets and books, Maximum respondents pay cash on delivery buying Flip kart.com was found their favourite site and Majority of respondents were agreed that online purchase saves time and price respectively.

6. References

- Mitchell Andrew D. Towards Capability: The Future of e-commerce within the global trading system: Journal of International Economic Law; c2001. p. 683-723.
- Kshetri Nir B. Determinants of the Locus of Global Ecommerce; Electronic market. 2001;l.11(4):250-257.
- Dasgupta Prithviraj, Sengupta Kasturi. E-commerce in the Indian Insurance Industry; electronic commerce Research. 2002;2(1):43-60.
- Girard T, Silverblatt R, Korgaonkar P. Influence of product class on preference for shopping on the internet. Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication. 2002 Oct 1;8(1):JCMC815.
- Burke RR. Technology and the customer interface: What consumers want in the physical and virtual store. Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science. 2002;30(4):411-432.
- Gefen D, Karahanna E, Straub DW. Trust and TAM in online shopping: An integrated model, MIS Quarterly. 2003;27(1):51-90.
- Christopher James. E-commerce: Comparison of online shopping Trends, Patterns and Preferences against a selected Survey of Women. 2004;42(3):270-278.
- Young Jun Choi, Chung Suk Suh. the death of Physical distance: An economic analysis of the emergence of electronic marketplaces. 2005;84(4):597-614.
- Gupta N, Handa M, Gupta B. Young adults of India-online surfers or online shoppers. Journal of Internet Commerce. 2008;7(4):425-444.
- Khare A, Singh S, Khare A. Innovativeness/novelty-seeking behavior as determinants of online shopping behavior among indian youth. Journal of Internet Commerce. 2010;9(3/4):164-185.
- Khare A, Rakesh S. Antecedents of online shopping behavior in India: An Examination. Journal of Internet Commerce. 2011;10(4):227-244.
- Gehrt K, Rajan M, Shainesh G, Czerwinski D, O’Brien M. Emergence of online shopping in India: shopping orientation segments. International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management. 2012;40(10):742-758.
- Goswami Adrita. Customer Satisfaction towards Online Shopping with Special Reference to Teenage Group of Jorhat Town Paripex - Indian Journal of Research. 2013 May 3(4):239-241.